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ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF MINING REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS IN THE ENFORCEMENT OF HEALTH AND SAFETY REGULATIONS FOR ARTISANAL AND SMALL SCALE MINING IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study is concerned with the impacts of Nigeria's regulatory provisions like the Mineral and Mining Act of 2007 on regulation of artisanal and small scale mining in the country, with specific emphasis on North-central Nigeria. It was aimed at ascertaining whether the efforts of Nigeria's the Mines Inspectorate Department led to adequate adherence to health and safety mining regulations amongst artisanal and small-scale miners in North-Central Nigeria. The study adopted the Critical Theory of Security and Rational Model of Policy Implementation. Both primary and secondary sources of data were utilized. Participant Observation, interviews and Documentary Methods of Data Collection were employed. Data was analyzed through the Qualitative Descriptive Method of analysis. Findings of the study revealed that adherence to health, safety laws amongst artisanal and small-scale miners is poor due to weak regulation of their activities. Sensitization of miners on global best practices in mining is limited. Amongst others, the study recommended that the Ministry of Mines and Steel should collaborate with the Ministry of Labour and Productivity in formulating standard occupational health and safety rules for artisanal and small-scale miners in Nigeria.*

Keywords: Regulatory Framework, Artisanal and Small-scale Mining, Health, Safety Regulations, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Despite the enormous potential of the mining sector with regards to revenue generation, employment creation and wealth generation, the sector makes negligible contributions to Nigeria's GDP, due to the largely unregulated nature of its activities. To Fayomi (2018), increase in the contribution of mining and quarrying to the nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which stands at 23.45% based on 2018 Q1 data, is an attestation to the fact that the potential of Nigeria's mining

sector to significantly contribute to its economy is quite promising.

Regardless of the enormous economic benefits, mining has its downside. By its very nature, mining inherently involves environmental degradation. Mining activities affect lands, air, water and associated flora and fauna, as well as the human environment, that is; individual health and safety, local community lifestyles, cultural survival, social order and economic wellbeing. Also, though the impacts of mining are said to be localized, it can cause national, trans-boundary and

global environmental problems (Pring, 1997). The realization of the enormous economic benefits of mining and the environmental, safety and health challenges it could present if left unregulated, led the Federal Government to enact the Nigerian Mineral and Mining Act of 2007. Other regulatory laws like the National Minerals and Metals policy of 2009, and the Mining regulations of 2011, which both sort to operationalize the provisions of the Mining Act of 2007 followed thereafter.

The Nigerian Mineral and Mining Act of 2007 made provision for various categories of licenses in an attempt to bring the bulk of mining operations under government control. At the centre of its efforts is the need to formalize artisanal and small-scale mining operations. The Act and its sister policies made provision for the creation of various units/departments, aimed at ensuring the proper implementation of the mining laws and policies enacted. The units include; the Mines inspectorate Department, the Mines Environmental Compliance Department, and the Small –scale Mining Department (CISLAC 2011). Since Mining operations and operators are domiciled within States and Local Governments, regardless of the fact that Mining is under the Federal Government Exclusive Legislative list, the Mining Act made provision for the creation of a Mineral Resource and Environmental Management Committee in each State. The Committees are to oversee mining operations at the state level (CISLAC, 2011). It is imperative to note at this juncture that the need to ensure protection of the environment, constitute part of the objectives of Sustainable Development Goals. This is captured under goal three (3). Based on the forgoing, this study is aimed at ascertaining whether the activities of the Mines Inspectorate Department

enhance adherence to health and safety regulations amongst artisanal and small scale-miners in North-central Nigeria.

RELEVANT HEALTH AND SAFETY REGULATIONS IN THE MINING INDUSTRY

Mining is a crucial industry that provides valuable resources for various sectors of the economy (Ericsson & Löf, 2019). However, due to its nature, mining poses significant risks to the health and safety of workers and the environment (Bansa et al, 2016). This has necessitated the implementation of stringent health and safety regulations to ensure the well being of individuals involved in mining activities and to mitigate adverse environmental impacts. Globally, mining regulations vary from country to country, depending on the specific conditions and requirements of each region. Many countries have established comprehensive frameworks that outline the standards and guidelines for mining operations, with a particular focus on health and safety aspects. These regulations cover various aspects of mining activities, including the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), prevention of water contamination, use of explosives, amongst others (Shen et al, 2015).

There are several global health and safety rules that guide mining activities, and these rules are implemented by various global agencies. Some of the major agencies and rules include:

International Labour Organization (ILO):

The ILO sets international labor standards, including standards for health and safety in the mining sector. The ILO's Safety and Health in Mines Convention, 1995 (No. 176) and its accompanying Recommendation (No. 183) provide guidelines for promoting and ensuring the safety and health of miners (Elgstrand et al,

2017). These guidelines aim to prevent accidents and diseases among miners, promote a safe working environment, and provide adequate training for workers.

Convention No. 176 requires member states to develop national laws and regulations that address safety and health issues in mines. These laws should cover areas such as ventilation, lighting, the use of explosives, machinery safety, and the prevention of fires and explosions (Hilgert, 2015). Employers are also required to provide regular health and safety training to their workers and to ensure that proper medical facilities are available in case of emergencies. Additionally, the convention emphasizes the importance of worker's participation in safety and health decision-making processes.

Recommendation No. 183 provides additional guidelines for promoting safety and health in mines, including the need for risk assessments, the establishment of emergency response plans, and the provision of personal protective equipment (Normlex, 2024). The recommendation also highlights the importance of monitoring the health of miners and providing them with access to occupational health services.

World Health Organization (WHO): The World Health Organization (WHO) has also established specific guidelines for mining activities to address occupational health hazards, exposure to toxic substances, and the management of health risks in mining communities. The guidelines stress the importance of monitoring and assessing health risks in mining operations, implementing controls to minimize exposures, and providing medical surveillance for workers. The WHO also recommends measures to protect the health of communities living near mining sites, such as monitoring air and water quality and promoting community engagement in health promotion activities.

United Nations Environment Program (UNEP): The UNEP works to address environmental health and safety issues in mining activities, including the management of mining waste and pollution prevention. The organization has specific rules for addressing environmental health and safety issues in mining activities. These rules focus on the management of mining waste and the prevention of pollution to minimize the impact of mining on the environment and human health (Desai, 2015). UNEP encourages the use of environmentally friendly mining practices, the restoration of mining sites after closure, and the promotion of sustainable mining solutions that balance economic development with environmental protection.

International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM): The ICMM is a global industry association that promotes responsible mining practices, including health and safety standards. The ICMM's 10 Principles for Sustainable Development set out guidelines for health and safety, environmental management, and community engagement in mining operations (ICMM). The principles aim to guide member companies in promoting responsible practices in health and safety, environmental management, and community engagement. The 10 principles are as follows:

1. Implement and maintain ethical business practices and sound systems of corporate governance.
2. Implement risk management strategies based on valid, reliable data and sound science
3. Seek continual improvement of health, safety, and environmental performance
4. Contribute to the conservation of biodiversity and integrated approaches to land use planning
5. Facilitate and encourage responsible product design, use, re-use, recycling, and disposal of our products

6. Contribute to the social, economic and institutional development of the communities in which we operate
7. Implement effective and transparent engagement, communication, and independently verified reporting arrangements with stakeholders
8. Implement human resource strategies that support a diverse workforce
9. Facilitate and encourage responsible growth and development of our businesses
10. Contribute to the protection of internationally proclaimed human rights

These principles are meant to ensure that mining activities are conducted in a responsible and sustainable manner, taking into account the well-being of workers, communities, and the environment.

MINING HEALTH AND SAFETY REGULATIONS IN NIGERIA

In Nigeria, the mining industry is governed by a set of regulations outlined in the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Act, which was established in 2007. This Act provides a legal framework for the regulation of the mining sector and is aimed at promoting the exploration, exploitation, processing, and utilization of mineral resources in a sustainable manner (Chukwuma et al, 2020). The Act empowers the Minister of Mines and Steel Development to regulate the sector and ensure compliance with health and safety standards.

As highlighted by Aram (2022), one of the major aspects of health and safety regulations in mining is the use of personal protective equipment (PPE). PPE is essential for protecting workers from various hazards in the mining environment, such as falling debris, chemicals, and dust. In Nigeria, mining regulations mandate that all mining companies provide their workers with adequate PPE, including helmets, goggles, gloves, and boots, amongst others (Mhlongo, 2021). Employers are required to

ensure that PPE is worn at all times during mining activities and that it is properly maintained and replaced when necessary.

Adherence to rules on the prevention of water contamination is another critical aspect of mining regulations (Agboola et al, 2020). As noted by scholars such as Madhav et al (2020), mining activities have the potential to pollute water sources through the release of chemicals and waste materials into water bodies. To prevent water contamination, provisions in the Nigerian Mining Act requires that mining companies in Nigeria implement effective wastewater management systems, such as sedimentation ponds and water treatment facilities (Adeniyi, 2022). These systems are designed to remove pollutants and contaminants from waste water before it is released into the environment, thus minimizing the risk of water pollution.

Rules on the use of explosives during mining operations are also strictly regulated under Nigerian law. Explosives are commonly used in mining activities to break up rocks and facilitate the extraction of minerals (Khademian & Bagherpour, 2017). However, the improper use of explosives can pose serious risks to the health and safety of workers and the surrounding communities. In Nigeria, provisions of the mining Act require that companies obtain permits from the relevant authorities before using explosives and to follow strict guidelines on their storage, handling, and disposal (Omokpariola & Omokpariola, 2021). This includes conducting regular safety inspections, providing training to workers on the safe use of explosives, and implementing measures to minimize the impact of blasting on the environment.

In addition to these specific regulations, mining companies in Nigeria are also required to comply with other general health and safety standards outlined in the Nigerian Minerals and Mining Regulations. These regulations cover a wide range of issues, including the

requirement that miners or mining corporations ensure that they provide ventilation in mines, provide adequate risk assessment and management plans, emergency response plans, and occupational health programmes. Mining companies are required to develop and implement comprehensive health and safety policies that address these issues and ensure the well-being of their workers. Despite the existence of these regulations, challenges remain in enforcing compliance and monitoring the implementation of health and safety standards in Nigeria's mining industry. As highlighted by Smith et al (2016), poor enforcement of regulations, inadequate resources, and lack of awareness among stakeholders are some of the issues that hinder the effective implementation of health and safety measures in mining operations.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

THE CRITICAL THEORY OF SECURITY

This study adopts the security perspective of the Critical theory. Proponents of the Critical perspective of security include scholars like; Campbell (1992), Mutimer (2009), Huysmans (2006) and Buzan (2018). They proposed an alternative approach to the understanding of security, which does not have the state as the major focus. A variant of this perspective is captured under the concept of human security. Human security proponents argue that threats to security, contrary to traditional opinions, do not always come from external sources.

For them, threats could in fact come from internal factors, situations or circumstances. Human security places emphasis on safety from violence, human rights and sustainable development. Within that context, some economic, health, environmental and personal issues which threaten the survival or well being of individuals are considered security issues. Those who subscribe to the idea of human security argue that freedom

from fear and want is threatened by issues like; conflicts,

economic and financial crises, ill health and national disasters. The forgoing could bring about sudden insecurity and deprivations (HSU-OCHA, 2009). Arguments of the critical perspective or theory of security can be summarized as follows:

1. The traditional approach to security which encourages wars, accumulation of weapons and so on has failed to ensure global security. Global security can only be achieved by ensuring the security of people/societies/communities, especially within nation-states.
2. Security efforts should focus more on protecting individuals. Individuals should be the major referent object in security, not the State. This is because individuals are the direct victims of insecurity.
3. Threats to security of a nation-state do not emanate mainly from other States or external factors or actors. They could also arise from internal factors related to challenges associated with poor resource management, exclusion and deprivation, underdevelopment, environmental degradation, food scarcity, inability to manage diversity, poor governance, and so on. Any sustainable solution to insecurity must take cognizance of the above listed factors.
4. The concept of security needs to be expanded to include issues of human rights and sustainable development, since they sometimes form the major underlying causes of violence or insecurity.
5. A State cannot be secure when it fails to address conditions or situations that threaten the well being of individuals within its domain, such as economic and health issues, amongst others.

THE RATIONAL MODEL OF POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

For this study, the Rational Model of Policy Implementation as espoused by Khan and Khakander (2016), was adopted. This model is anchored on the premise that every policy implementation needs to have clearly spelt out goals, missions and objectives; intensive/detailed planning; proper task/job assignments; effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms; comprehensive and efficient operative procedures; and the appropriate approaches required to aid implementers in defining the extent of their responsibilities, based on set policy objectives. The basic propositions of this model are captured in number hypotheses. As captured in Khan and Khakander (2016), the following are the hypotheses or propositions of the Rational Model of policy implementation:

1. Clearer goals, objectives and targets present better chances for the effective implementation of a policy.
2. Accurate and consistent planning increases the possibility for successful policy implementation.
3. Setting clear/detailed tasks, and assigning them adequately, leads to better implementation performance.
4. Accurate/ effective standardization, improves policy implementation performance.
5. Greater levels of monitoring, increases the possibility of successful policy implementation.

The relationship between the nature of a policy, as well as implementation approach, and implementation performance, is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between the nature of a policy, implementation approach, and implementation performance

Source: Khan and Khakander (2016).

METHODOLOGY

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

This study adopted the Participant Observation, In-depth Interview and Documentary Methods of Data Collection. Mining areas within Plateau and Nasarawa States, specifically; New Abuja area, and Kwang, Jos South Local Government, Plateau States and communities within Wamba Local Government in Nasarawa State, were visited for field observations on multiple occasions, between September, 2018 and September, 2023.

Due to the sensitive nature of mining operations, especially with regards to the involvement of locals and even the alleged involvement of prominent personalities in illegal mining operations, it was observed that people were reluctant to divulge information. Hence, to gain trust, the researcher posed as a solids minerals buyer/dealer. This allowed for close interaction with miners at the mining sites, as well as solid mineral buyers/dealers, and gave room for close observation. Pictures were taken as evidence.

Also, besides the on-site observation and interactions, data was collected through in-depth interviews conducted with a total of eight (8) respondents. The Purposive Sampling Method was used to select respondents who are knowledgeable about mining operations in North-central Nigeria and are directly or indirectly linked with such operations. Three (3) of the respondents are Geologists who have previously participated in mining operations within the North-central region. Two (2) are persons involved in solid minerals trade, while the remaining three (3) are local miners, operating within Nasarawa and Plateau State. The Documentary Method of Data Collection was used to extract relevant information from secondary sources such as; Journals, Books, Online articles, and so on.

Data collected was analyzed through the Qualitative Descriptive Method of data analysis. This method of analysis was chosen because the nature of data generated is qualitative. Tables and figures were used in the analysis. The Qualitative Descriptive Method of Data Analysis involves the identification of related patterns, themes or ideas, and organization of the themes or ideas in such a way that it provides a logical explanation for a phenomenon, and also provides basis for generalization or future projections. Content Analysis is an integral part of this approach to data analysis, and was employed to make meaning of the information gathered.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

USE OF PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT

Recommendation No. 183 of the International Labour Organization's (ILO) rules on mining requires the use of personal protective equipment when carrying out mining operations (Normlex, 2024). Health and Safety regulations under the Nigerian Mining Act also require that miners use protective equipment during mining (Agboola et al, 2020). Contrary to the forgoing provisions, the observations made at the mining sites visited and on-site interviews with some miners showed a lack of concern for health and safety matters. Despite the fact that rock falls, pit collapses, and dust are some of the biggest risks factors in Artisanal and Small Scale Mining (ASM), the miners can be seen digging deep holes, without helmets, protective shoes, masks to curtail dust inhalation, coverall wears, and so on.

International Labour Organization (ILO) guidelines only recommend highly supervised use of explosives during mining activities. Similarly, provisions of the Nigerian Mining Act require that companies

obtain permits from the relevant authorities before using explosives and to follow strict guidelines on their storage, handling, and disposal of minerals and mining waste. However, contrary to the forgoing provisions, interactions with miners confirmed the speculations on the high rate of mining accidents, due to unsupervised and unauthorized use of explosives in mining operations. The researcher observed that there is little or no provision for first aid services. In addition, unsupervised explosive use is prevalent. Interaction with miners in Nasarawa and Plateau States shows a constant use of explosives to blast rocks during mining. One of the miners interviewed said “In the course of digging, when we encounter rocks or areas difficult to break through, we make use of explosives to blast the rocks”. When asked about the source of the explosives, the miners interviewed declined to respond. One of the Geologists interviewed who resides around the Kwang area of Jos stated that the activities of artisanal miners in the area was largely unregulated, considering that inspection officers do not visit mining sites. In his own words:

The Local miners in this area operate on their own. Most of them sell the minerals mined like Tin to Chinese buyers. People are reluctant to approach the miners because they have organized themselves into gangs and can be violent. So far, the authorities have done little or nothing to regulate their activities (Field work, 2019).

The implication of the above is that the use of explosives is unsupervised. The rules state that use of explosives should be supervised by experts. However, this is not the case. This unsupervised use of explosives often leads to seismic disturbances. Interestingly, most of the miners seen at the sites do not use ear plugs to mitigate the impact of the noise caused by explosives. Interactions with the miners also showed that they had little or no

knowledge about rules guiding the use of explosives. There is almost zero regulation. Evidences from secondary day sources also show that the unregulated use of explosives is prevalent in the other states under study. Plates 1a and b show what the ideal wears for mining activities should look like.

(a)

(b)

Plates 1a and b: Appropriate Personal Protective Equipment

Source: Williams (2016). Plates 2a and b clearly shows what exist in the study area. In plates 2a and b it can be seen that miners dig holes, without any form of protective wears, whether boots, helmets, or face masks.

(a)

(b)

Plates 2a and b: Miners at a Tin Mining Site in Nassarawa State, conducting Mining Activities without proper protective outfits

Source: Field Work (2023).

The scenario in Plates 2a and b is the same in other places around Plateau, Kogi and Niger States, where small scale and artisanal mining activities take place. Due to these practices, miners face risks associated with respiratory diseases, cancer, neurotoxicity, airborne diseases like tuberculosis, injury as a result of rock falls and mine collapses, as well as cardiovascular diseases (Smith, et al, 2016). When asked whether inspectors visit the camps regularly to sensitize them about safety rules, responses from the miners revealed the opposite.

In a mining site at New Abuja in Jos, Plateau State, the miners stated that they were

unaware of any agency or rules, created to regulate their activities. No standard dressing codes for artisanal miners in Nigeria are in existence. This partly accounts for the implementation challenges. Infiltration of toxic metals into homes becomes worse when mining outfits are not separate from the cloths used in the home.

ADHERENCE TO RULES ON PREVENTION OF WATER CONTAMINATION

The Nigerian Mining Act of 2007 is the major legal framework guiding the operation of mining activities in Nigeria. The provisions of the Nigerian Mining Act on Health and safety requires that mining organizations operating in Nigeria implement effective waste water management systems, such as sedimentation ponds and water treatment facilities (Adeniyi et al. 2022). This is in alignment with the provisions of the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) which requires that miners ensure the effective management of mining waste and the prevention of pollution to minimize the impact of mining on the environment and human health and the provisions of the International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM), which requires that mining activities be conducted in a manner that protects the biodiversity, including the water bodies and land (ICMM, 2024).

It is the responsibility of the Mines Inspectorate Department; a unit under the Ministry of Mines and Steel, to enforce rules which protect water bodies and even underground water during mining activities. Evidences on ground shows that the department failed in that regard. On-site observations made by the researcher, who visited mining sites indicated that local populations within the mining communities and even miners themselves showed little knowledge about the impacts which mining activities could have on water bodies. Most processing practices adopted by the Artisanal

and small-scale mineral miners in the sites visited are hazardous to health and environment.

For instance, it was observed that some miners wash solid minerals mined, directly in the Streams and Rivers which serve as major sources of water and other aquatic resources, for host communities. Observations made in mining sites within Nasarawa State revealed that some mining sites are located close to Streams and Rivers, which are connected to major sources of water in the area. Miners were seen washing mined Tins directly in streams. Knowledge on the impacts of mine tailings on health, especially due to the possible presence of heavy metals was obviously limited or non-existent. Miners, who manage to get alternative sources of water, do little or nothing to prevent water from running into streams or rivers, especially due to the fact that some of the mines are located besides rivers or streams. The picture below was taken in wamba, Nassarawa state. It shows miners washing mined Tin directly in a Stream which serves as a major source of water for the community.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Plates 3a, b and c: Miners in Wamba, Nassarawa State, Separating Mined Tin from Tailings/Ore by washing Mined directly in Streams/Rivers

Source: Field Work (2018)

Evidences from previous studies also show that small scale and artisanal mining operations in Kogi State have had devastating effect on the soil and water bodies in the area. Reports published by Olapoju (2016) and Kimani (2017), on unregulated coal mining activities of the Eta Zuma mining company in Okobo and Okaba, all under Ankpa Local Government Area, showed the harmful effect it has had on water bodies within the area.

In Okobo, coal mining operations was said to have contaminated the water supply of the community. Residents lament over the contamination of streams, to the extent that the water cannot be used for bathing. According to Olapoju, over time, coal mining activities in Okobo caused heavy metals contamination of water bodies, around mine sites, rendering them acidic and highly toxic. Olapoju cited the result of a study conducted by Global Rights on the impact of coal mining activities in Okobo. The findings of the study by Global Rights revealed high levels of Copper, Calcium, Chromium, Phosphate and Manganese. The metals were found in soil samples, located about 10meters away from a mining pit. Considering that these finding applies to both wet and dry season, the tendency of the metals running into streams and rivers during the rainy season is high. Plates 4a and b are showing contaminated

streams/Rivers in Okobo, due to Coal Mining activities.

(a)

(b)

Plates 4a and b: Streams in Okobo, Ankpa Local Government, Kogi State, due to Cola Mining Activities

Source: Olapoju (2016).

A community Youth leader interviewed by Olapoju (2016) stated that there are no Mines Environmental Compliance Officers in Kogi State. We can deduce from this that mines inspectors have not also frequented the area to check the practices in the mining sites. What this means therefore is that the coal mining activity has been operating without proper regulations. An environmental assessment report, submitted before the company received its license in 2012, to commence operations, showed the impacts which the mining operations would have on the host

community. Ideally, it should have also showed how the company intends to mitigate

the adverse effects. The company should never have been allowed to commence mining operations, since they obviously lack the technology needed to manage/curtail the health and environmental consequences that could surface. In 2014, the community leaders of Okobo declined to sign a community development agreement, granting the company permission to continue its operations, due to some factors associated with the issues raised above. They were sidelined, and the unregulated coal mining operations continued.

MINERAL PROCESSING PRACTICES AND STORAGE PRACTICES

The reality on ground in states visited (Plateau and Nasarawa States) shows that processing practices amongst small and medium scale miners still fall below international standards. The Mining guidelines provided by the World Health Organization (WHO), requires that mining activities be conducted in a manner that addresses occupational health hazards, minimizes exposure to toxic substances, and enhances the management of health risks in mining communities. Provisions of the Nigerian Mining Act on health and safety also aim to promote the exploration, exploitation, processing and utilization of mineral resources in a sustainable manner (Chukwuma et al, 2020).

What the forgoing entails is that miners adopt mineral processing and storage practices that limits the direct exposure of miners, households or members of the mining host communities to toxic/harmful chemicals/substances. On the contrary, the on-site visits to mining communities in Nasarawa and Plateau indicate that the local miners employ unsafe mineral processing and storage practices.

From the on-site interactions with miners at the sites visited in Plateau and Nasarawa States, the on-site observations made by the researcher and interviews held with other key informants, it was found that the process of milling/crushing to extract minerals is still conducted with basic technological tools like mortar, pestle, grinding stones, calabash, and so on. While having an on-site interaction with some of the miners at the mining sites, the researcher found that the miners do take the solid minerals mined, back to their homes for processing. The researcher also found that miners do not just take ores home, but they store them in home utensils, which are used for domestic activities in the homes. The researcher also found that the process of grinding and sieving is conducted with the bare hand. No protective wears are used. Going by the description obtained from miners, by the researchers, Plates 5a and b show what artisanal solid minerals processing practices looks like in the areas visited.

(a)

(b)

Plates 5a and b: Local Solid Minerals Processing Practices

Sources: Asha Tanna (2013).

DISCUSSIONS

Artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM) activities play a significant role in Nigeria's economy, as it provides a means of livelihoods for numerous individuals in rural areas (Osumanu, 2020). However, there are glaring deficiencies in the enforcement of health and safety regulations within the mining sector. The findings indicate a lack of compliance with protective equipment usage, water contamination prevention measures, and proper processing and storage practices among miners in these regions.

The non-adherence to safety regulations, particularly concerning the use of protective equipment, is of serious concern as it exposes miners to various health hazards. Studies such as that conducted by Wireko-Gyebi (2022) indicates that the absence of helmets, protective shoes, and masks during mining activities, puts individuals at risk of injuries from falling debris, exposure to harmful substances, and respiratory problems. Additionally, the study conducted by Shriwas & Pritchard (2020) indicates that the unauthorized and unsupervised use of explosives for mining operations further

The disregard for rules on preventing water contamination is another critical issue identified in the study. Directly washing mined minerals in streams and rivers not only pollutes the water sources but also endangers the health of communities reliant on these bodies of water (Minnaar, 2020). The practice of using water sources for both mining activities and domestic needs poses a significant threat to public health and underscores the urgent need for stricter regulations and enforcement mechanisms in the mining sector. Also, the continued use of rudimentary methods for processing and storing mined minerals highlights a lack of

technological advancement and proper infrastructure within the Artisanal and Small-Scale Mining (ASM) sector in Nigeria. Grinding stones, mortar and pestle, and calabashes are inefficient tools for mineral extraction and can lead to substantial waste generation and environmental degradation. Furthermore, storing mined products in home utensils increases the risk of chemical exposure for miners and their families, potentially resulting in severe health consequences such as poisoning.

Similar studies conducted on small scale mining operations indicate that other countries also face similar challenges like those faced in Nigeria, when it comes to enforcing health and safety regulations on small scale and artisanal miners. A study conducted by Zvarivadza and Nhleko (2018) show that in South Africa, challenges of enforcing regulations in ASM operations exist and have led to unsafe working conditions and environmental deterioration. Similarly, another study by Hilson (2020) indicates that other countries in sub-Saharan Africa like Zimbabwe are also grappling with regulatory challenges, when it comes to artisanal and small-scale mining.

Findings of this study underscores the urgent need for enhanced regulatory frameworks and enforcement mechanisms in Nigeria's ASM sector, in order to promote safe and environmentally sustainable mining practices. Addressing the gaps in compliance with health and safety regulations, water contamination prevention measures, and processing and storage practices is crucial to protecting the well-being of miners and communities. Collaborative efforts involving government agencies, mining associations, and local communities are essential in fostering a culture of responsible mining and ensure the long-term viability of the sector.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings on the role of Nigeria's Mines Inspectorate Department in enforcing health and safety rules in mining reveal that they have failed in that regard. Observations made during field trips to some mining communities and information gathered from secondary sources show that constant inspection of artisanal/small scale mining sites/operations by officials from the federal government is almost non-existent or very limited. There is little sensitization of local miners about the health and safety implications of certain mining practices. There is little knowledge on the part of miners about existing rules or even regulatory bodies.

Findings of this study show a lack of regard for use of protective gears/ outfits during mining operations, despite the constant cases of mine collapses, and dangerous impacts of blasting measures like the indiscriminate use of explosives. It also found the prevalence of practices that could cause water contamination like separation of solid minerals from tailings by washing directly in streams/ rivers that serve as a major source of water for host communities.

Also, little is done to divert water used in processing from getting into streams/ rivers. This accounts for the lead poisoning that occurred in Niger state, Nigeria. In addition, the study found a prevalence of rudimentary mineral processing practices, which is conducted even in homes. Storage of amalgams at home for processing, and even the use of domestic utensils for processing and storage, is prevalent. This could lead to food contamination. It was also found that small-scale mining companies do little or nothing to prevent water contamination. The situation in Okobo community, Kogi state, is a case in point. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Ministry of Mines and Steel should collaborate with the Ministry of labour and productivity, in articulating/formulating standard occupational safety and health rules for small-scale and artisanal miners in Nigeria. The rules should take into consideration, the peculiarities of artisanal and small-scale mining, especially with regards to the abilities/capabilities of those involved.
2. Technical and funding support, directed at providing proper mine site facilities/equipment, like protective wears, hand washing and cloth changing sections, first aid materials, etc should be provided. The Mines Inspectorate should have offices in artisanal and small-scale mining flashpoints. This would make it easier for them to conduct mine inspections and ensure that safety and health rules are being addressed.
3. The Mines Inspectorate Department should constantly organize sensitization programmes to educate artisanal and small-scale miners on health and safety issues. Specific emphasis should be placed on the need for use of protective wears, methods of avoiding water contamination, the need to exclude children from mining operations due to the peculiar dangers they face, etc. Host communities should be made part of the process, since they are usually direct victims of the accidents that occur due to mining.
4. A system which prevents artisanal miners from carrying out solid minerals processing should be developed. This would limit the danger of exposure of miners and host communities to toxic chemicals. The government should find a way to

compensate artisanal miners for exploration and extraction, while the processing of mined minerals should be left to the government or bigger companies that are better equipped to handle that. Only small-scale miners who have capability and adequate knowledge to conduct processing operations safely, should be allowed to do so.

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